

The Flexibility of a CLIL Teacher**Linguistics**

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Abstract

This study is included in the action-research of doctorate that I am carrying out on "The necessary professional competences of a CLIL teacher " that is developed in the field of Education of the University of La Laguna. The aim of the research is to study the necessary professional teaching skills for the CLIL teachers, in the context of the Canary Islands. Firstly, a summary is presented on the teaching field of CLIL and an analysis and a comparative study will be carried out on which subjects are appropriate for CLIL teaching, according to different models and contexts. Secondly, there will be some key axes to classify the teaching competences in relation to CLIL teaching, according to different proposals of experts in this subject and it will be proposed a professional teaching competence that can act as a catalyst for the rest, teachers' flexibility.

Introduction

Nowadays, the concept of school is not reduced to a mere place of learning, but it constitutes a space for the exchange of knowledge that, together with the learning of skills, abilities, skills and attitudes will be fundamental for an academic, personal development and full social, both of the students and teachers and the rest of the educational community. The way to learn and communicate is in a process of constant change so the way of teaching must also adapt and integrate elements and tools that are useful in daily life, present and future "lifelong learning."

The CLIL teaching provides an approach that can be described as "flexible and inclusive that can be applied through many specific methodologies where both language and content are integrated" (Coyle et al., 2010). In CLIL teaching it is important to know what subjects are suitable for this type of learning, in order to avoid the difficulties of teachers in the classroom by facilitating the definition of a CLIL teaching profile. In this way, the article includes the analysis and comparison on the most appropriate subjects for CLIL teaching according to different educational models, starting from the experiences of Canada, Europe and concluding in our educational context of the Canary Islands with the PILE Plan.

In turn, the study and analysis of the curricular content to be taught is not enough to define the competences of a CLIL teacher. To ensure that learning in this type of teaching is effective, it is necessary for teachers to be in possession of a series of specific professional competences for teaching CLIL. Teachers must be more flexible and adapt their methodology to this more competent approach, since not only must they handle the curricular contents that they are going to teach, but also they must develop a series of specific skills of this type of teaching and put them into practice. simultaneous and integrated in the CLIL approach. Teaching flexibility is considered

as a competence that acts as a regulating element of the rest of professional competences, in order to respond effectively to the difficulties and needs of the students.

In conclusion, this study aims to outline a referential axis of general competencies of CLIL teachers, following models of competence provided by experts in this field. In turn, know what subjects are appropriate in this type of education, according to different models starting from Canada, following the European model and ending in the context of the Canary Islands. All these factors will favor the definition of a CLIL teaching profile, where flexibility allows an effective competence development.

CLIL

The term "Content and Language Integrated Learning" (CLIL) was first defined in 1994 by David Marsh as "situations in which the subjects or part of the subjects are taught through a foreign language with a dual objective, learning of contents and the simultaneous learning of a foreign language" (Marsh, 1994). This concept, which has been adapted to Spanish with the acronym CLIL "Integrated Learning of Curricular Knowledge and Foreign Language" has an increasing presence in the educational system of our country.

The Educational Social Network "Euroclil" considers CLIL as "a dual educational approach focused on the fact that an additional language is used for the teaching and learning of content and language" (Attard et al., 1994). Euroclil shares the same point of view as David Marsh, considering CLIL teaching as an integrating method of curricular content and a foreign language. This inclusive approach provides meaningful learning for students who work on the contents of the curriculum using a foreign language as a communication vehicle.

One year later, continuing in the European educational context, the Council Resolution of 1995 issued a report on CLIL education by Frigols and Marsh, in which it reveals that CLIL "refers to the promotion of innovative methods and in particular to the teaching of non-linguistic disciplines through a foreign language facilitating bilingual teaching" (Frigols et al., 2014). In turn, the white paper of the commission in 1995 made mention of CLIL teaching in the European Schools and proposed that this type of teaching be considered in the rest of the centers, where the foreign language they learn was used to impart curricular contents and therefore impact on inclusive CLIL education (European Commission, 1995). During the 1990s, CLIL continued giving much to talk about in the European context (Marsh, et al., 1999: p.17, cited in Coyle et al., 2010) "CLIL within the European context was used to describe a design of good practices achieved in different types of school settings where teaching and learning took place in the language "so that content and language are used in a parity way in CLIL teaching.

In the context of the Canary Islands, the Plan for Promoting Foreign Languages of the Canary Islands (PILE), which is based on the LOMCE, promotes learning opportunities among students, using foreign languages as a vehicle. This plan has begun to be implemented in the centers in the academic year 2016/2017, specifically in fourteen infant and primary schools. Through contextualized learning, interdisciplinary teaching and the CLIL approach, this plan aims at "the acquisition of at least one foreign language through integrated content and language learning". Currently, this plan continues in the pilot centers that began to carry it out last year and also in other centers selected by the Ministry of Education where it will continue to be implemented progressively.

A crucial aspect in CLIL / AICLE teaching is the methodology, because it must be diverse according to the different realities of each classroom and thus be able to adapt to the needs of our students. "CLIL is an educational method in which various methodologies are used to carry out the dual approach where attention is given to both language and content [...] including the merging of elements which may have previously been separated as they are to the subjects in the curriculum" (Coyle et al., 2010). Coyle and Marsh propose an inclusive and interdisciplinary teaching in terms of content and language and also among the different curricular contents provided by the regulations, in order to achieve a teaching of interrelated contents based on the needs and realities of the students and thus achieve meaningful learning for the learner that will serve as competencies for solving problems.

The CLIL approach provides the perspective of an inclusive and integrative teaching of language and content, however, not all definitions agree on what subjects of the curriculum should be put into practice. The choice of which subjects should be included in the CLIL programs has been a subject of discussion, (Pavesi et al., 2001) deal with this subject starting from the definition of the CLIL concept "as the teaching of a subject (but not the subject of language) through a foreign language or a second language ", so the description they make of CLIL is inclusive with the contents, but, nevertheless, they limit the use of this approach in the subjects of the curriculum that deal with contents of the native language Taking into account the vision of the Education Information Network in the European Community "Eurydice" takes into account the subjects in CLIL teaching and "describes all types of provision in which a second language (foreign, regional, minority language or other official language) of the state) is used to teach certain subjects in the curriculum different from the language classes themselves" (Eurydice, 2006), therefore, there is an idea to delimit the use of CLIL in some particular subjects, but it makes a differentiation between the teaching of content through the use of a foreign language and a foreign language content class in itself.

In short, the CLIL educational approach proposes a more inclusive and inclusive vision in the teaching of languages and content. At the same time, a division is made between the curricular contents of foreign languages and the teaching of curricular contents using foreign languages, the latter being an effective teaching adapted to the reality of the student body. In this way, CLIL

teaching can not be a particular approach to teaching foreign languages, but rather it is proposed as a model of competency education throughout life. The students will have in their hands an integrating tool that will provide them with meaningful learning, which will be useful during the situations they face in their future.

Appropriate Subjects in the CLIL Approach

Among the issues that concern CLIL, one of the topics that has generated more discussions is, what subjects are suitable to be included in this educative program. Since the seventies, in Quebec (Canada) began to implement the first language immersion programs, certain subjects took greater weight within these programs with respect to others. The first experiences were carried out with a group of English-speaking children, where the French language was introduced. It was developed by "linguistic showers" of 20-30 minutes per day by native English teachers, so their skills in French were very scarce. Figure 1 shows the number of weekly hours taught in each subject in this language immersion program. It highlights the large amount of time spent on subjects such as Arithmetic and Linguistic Skills, considered as fundamental elements in education at that time. In addition, they were common subjects to all the courses of the academic stage of Primary Education.

Arithmetic.	20 hours.
Art.	06 hours.
Writing.	03 hours.
Music.	04 hours.
Physical education.	06 hours.
Religion and health..	07 hours.
Library.	02 hours.
Science.	04 hours.
Geography.	06 hours.
Social studies.	01 hour.
History.	04 hours.
Linguistic skills.	82 hours.
Personal development.	02 hours.

Table 1: Number of weekly hours in the language immersion program.

Years later, these first language immersion programs give way to CLIL teaching in Europe. The proposal made by Eurydice on the CLIL approach in Europe, establishes a series of organizational guidelines that regulate the action of the educational administrations of the different countries of the union. In accordance with these guidelines, the subject of Science and / or Social Sciences are considered appropriate for the delivery of CLIL or CLIL in Primary Education in: Albania, Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia-Herzegovina and Switzerland and in the Secondary stage in:

Switzerland, Germany, Czech Republic, United Kingdom, Estonia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Serbia, Romania, Macedonia and Albania. At the same time, it considers the teaching of Art, sport or science in Primary in places like: Estonia, Corsica and Sardinia.

However, in Secondary there is a combination of Science, Art and Sport in: Finland, Sweden, Latvia, Bulgaria and the Netherlands. If we focus our eyes on Spain, we can say that our country has freedom of choice in the subjects to be taught in the CLIL programs. As a consequence, in the Canary Islands each of the centers participating in the PILE Plan is free to offer any subject as part of the program, in accordance with the guidelines established by Eurydice. So the fact that some subjects are taught more frequently than others has more to do with the human resources available at the time, than with a true consensus on the part of educational institutions.

Figure 1: Map of the European Union about subjects taught in CLIL teaching (Eurydice, 2006).

Figure 2: Subjects taught in the Pilot Centers, PILE Plan, in the school year 2016-2017.

Teaching Professional Competence

Competencies can be described as skills and tools that try to provide answers to problems and conflicts that arise in our daily lives. In the current educational reality, teachers need to possess and develop professional skills to perform their work effectively and to be able to train competent citizens of the 21st century.

In this way, teachers' professional competences are the set of skills common to all teacherdepartments in their professional practice. However, CLIL teaching requires specific competences for the development of this complex educational approach. As a result of what was previously described about the double inclusive focus of this teaching, these competences will revolve around two fundamental aspects: curricular content and language. However, these will not be the only professional necessary skills for CLIL teachers, since they must adapt to the plurilingual reality we live in, the context in which it develops, the reality of the classroom, the needs of students, etc. Gutiérrez (2013) explains that it is essential "the ongoing training of teachers who participate in CLIL programs is essential for the quality and effectiveness of these programs to be maintained and for the achievement of objectives by students to be optimal".

Regarding the organization of the specific professional competences of a CLIL teacher, (Whitty, 1996, p.89-90, cited in Katarzyna, 2013) determines that the competences of a CLIL teacher can be included in the following categories: "professional values, professional development, communication, subject knowledge, understanding of learners and their learning ". That is to say, the teacher programs and plans the learning situations to be taught in his CLIL classroom, in addition he understands that the continuous training is part of his professional practice to, in this way, achieve greater success in the learning of his students; communicates clearly, accurately and effectively in a foreign language, dominates the curricular content of the subject to be taught and is able to understand the students and evaluate the learning processes.

Marsh in turn, exposes a series of professional competences, according to the educational elements that the teacher has present in his classroom programming: "language and communication, theory, methodology, learning environment, materials development and assessment" (Marsh et al., 2001). Again, for a CLIL teacher, knowledge of the language and curricular content are essential elements in the teaching competencies, communication is the vehicular medium of the transmission and understanding of contents, the CLIL methodology must be participatory and active, contextualised learning It will provide the acquisition of meaningful knowledge for students, the development of their own materials and adapted to CLIL teaching and the evaluation of teaching-learning processes.

The document "European framework for CLIL teacher education" (Marsh et al., 2012) proposes that CLIL teachers receive specific training that provides them with tools for the acquisition of these professional skills. These are organized in this way: "personal reflection", the

CLIL teacher understands and interacts with the students; "CLIL fundamentals", teachers dominate the various CLIL methodologies in the classroom and integrate them into the student learning process; "Content and Language awareness" exposes the capacity for inference from L1 to L2 together with the curricular contents to be imparted, which must be encouraged by a teacher to achieve successful learning; "Methodology and assessment", is the ability to integrate diverse and varied methodologies and evaluation procedures that favor meaningful learning for students; "Research and evaluation" explains that teachers themselves must be able to investigate and reflect on their own teaching action to improve their professional skills and thus promote the success of their students' learning; "Learning resources and environments" shows that CLIL teachers must provide their students with knowledge structures or scaffolding, which facilitate the construction of contextualized and integrated knowledge; "Classroom management" states that teachers must encourage and motivate active and participatory dynamics in the CLIL classroom; and finally "CLIL management" deals with the fact that CLIL teaching is not a content that reaches only inside of the classroom, but that it tries to involve the whole educational community and the society to which we belong.

Newby in the document "European profile for language teachers in training" (Newby et al., 2007) organizes a series of professional teacher competencies that teachers must acquire for the development of their professional practice. These competences are organized into general competences, which underlie more specific ones and are classified as follows. In the first place, "interpersonal competence" aims for the teacher to be able to generate a good classroom climate, attend to students in a personalized manner, understand the context surrounding the students and educate the students, taking into account the diversity cultural. Secondly, "the pedagogical competence" tries to carry out diverse methodologies and evaluation procedures, in addition, the teacher must be aware of the educational regulations and capable of developing a research and self-critical vision in his teaching work. Third, the "knowledge of the subjects and methods of teaching" refers to the mastery of linguistic communication, apply the content of the educational curriculum in an efficient way, develop the Basic Competences in the center, use the Tics effectively and in educational context and apply various evaluation procedures and methodologies that adapt to the needs of students and teach them to cooperate and collaborate with each other. Fourth, "organizational competence" deals with the disposition and grouping of students in the classroom to develop various types of learning, such as the cooperative, in addition to the teacher must have knowledge about the management of centers and the creation and development of educational projects. Fifth, "competition for collaboration with colleagues" exposes being able to work in a collaborative group. Sixth, "competition for collaboration with the environment" explains that it is necessary to create networks both within the school environment and with other educational institutions in the same or different countries and in turn, strengthen the link of the school with families. Seventh and finally, "the competence for reflection and professional development" determines that the teacher must receive continuous training on foreign languages, ICTs and be self-critical and investigate in what aspects can improve their professional practice.

Likewise, experts in the field of teacher professional competencies such as Hansen-Pauly consider it appropriate to organize the professional competencies of CLIL teachers in eight categories: (Hansen-Pauly, 2009, cited in Pavón, 2013).

1. The students' needs.
2. Planning and programming.
3. Diversity of methodologies.
4. Interaction.
5. Literary matters.
6. Evaluation.
7. Cooperation.
8. Reflection, context and culture.

In short, the dual approach of language and content typical of CLIL teaching is once again the axis on which the teaching competences revolve in their categorization. In addition to the essential competences associated with these two elements, the authors previously cited provide other key factors that must be taken into account such as the educational context.

- The curricular content.
- The foreign language and culture.
- Planning and programming learning situations.
- Proposing various, active and participatory methodologies and evaluation procedures that pay attention to students' needs in the classroom.
- Contextualized learning.
- Knowing the CLIL educational approach.
- The teacher as a researcher of his own educational practice.
- Promoting situations of cooperative and collaborative work.

These key factors for CLIL teaching are translated into professional competences that CLIL/AICLE teachers must possess and develop in their educational practice. In this way, the competences are not exclusive or closed, in contrast, they are a range of skills that must allow the introduction, modification and adaptation of them according to the context and educational needs that we have in the CLIL classroom.

The Flexibility of a CLIL Teacher

The professional competences of the CLIL teachers, proposed by the previously mentioned authors, represent useful tools in teacher training that aim to solve the possible deficiencies and difficulties that arise in the delivery of a CLIL / CLIL class. The effectiveness of these skills is truncated or hindered in its implementation, if the set of skills and abilities is not introduced in an integrated and simultaneous in classroom situations.

The ability to implement the set of professional skills in an inclusive manner and adapted to the students' needs in different educational contexts requires teaching flexibility. The educator develops this skill by adapting the use of the foreign language, the curricular content it teaches, the learning situations, the methodologies and evaluation procedures, the CLIL approach, contextualized learning, group work and the critical and reflective sense of the educator himself. Teaching flexibility can be considered as a professional competence in itself, which acts as a catalyst for other skills or abilities in CLIL teaching.

In the first place, the CLIL teacher must be able to be flexible in the use of the foreign language by modulating the lexicon he uses, the speed in oral communication, the number of interventions in the classroom and the type of registration of the language he uses in the classroom. Secondly, the content will be adapted to the needs of the students and will be taught in a way that is related to their near reality. Third, the teacher has to foresee in their programming and planning of learning situations the possible difficulties that the students will present and thus, put forward solutions that facilitate their learning. Fourth, both methodologies and evaluation procedures must be diverse, precisely to adapt to the needs of students and to make the most of the learning situations in the classroom and thus achieve useful and meaningful learning for students. Fifth, if the student's learning is contextualized not only in their near reality, but in the cultural and social values of the vehicular language, this learning will involve an adequate cognitive and personal development of the student, in terms of the integration of the content and language as useful tools for your life in different contexts. Sixth, the teacher must be in possession of adequate knowledge about the CLIL approach and have the ability to develop it effectively in the classroom. Seventh, the group work will be essential for the personal and social development of the students, since this type of organization will favor the development of cooperative and personal strategies among equals. Finally, in eighth place, the role of the teacher is developed, both as a professional in teaching and as a researcher of his own teaching activity; Through reflection and self-criticism, the teacher will improve his teaching action, thus favoring student learning success.

At present, the objectives in education lie in creating and generating competent citizens, who acquire a series of skills and abilities in the school that are useful tools attached to their cognitive, personal and social training for the exercise of their life. Teaching flexibility is proposed as the competence that modulates the rest of the competences and subcompetences that make up the set of skills and tools of CLIL teachers. Taking this into consideration, it will be the teacher's task to be flexible and adapt all the teaching skills and elements that influence student learning.

Conclusion

Society is in a constant state of change and needs to learn tools and competencies that are useful for the resolution of conflicts throughout life. This change affects both the way of teaching and the way of learning and is reflected in the CLIL / AICLE teaching, because it is a competence

education. Teaching professional competences are a fundamental part in the training of an educator. These are tools that allow teachers to teach meaningful and quality teaching to their students.

Prior to the CLIL approach, during the 1970s in Canada, language immersion programs began to be implemented to promote learning through the use of a foreign language. Later, in 1994, David Marsh translates previous linguistic experiences into a more inclusive and inclusive approach known as CLIL (AICLE, in Spanish). In the European context, Eurydice establishes a series of guidelines on what subjects should be included in CLIL learning in the countries that make up the European Union. According to this European CLIL map, Spain is included in the category of countries that can freely choose which subjects are taught in the CLIL / AICLE programs. So in the geographical context of the Canary Islands, the PILE Plan aims to promote CLIL education, without specifying which subjects are attached to this program, but each center with the human resources it has, decide in which subjects can be applied the CLIL approach.

The subjects to be taught within the CLIL program determine in part the profile of the CLIL teacher. Educators must master these curricular contents and, in turn, it is necessary to integrate and develop a series of specific teaching professional competences in CLIL teachers. These skills are interrelated with the curricular content, the foreign language, planning and programming of learning situations, methodologies and diverse evaluation procedures, CLIL / AICLE teaching domain, contextualized learning, collaborative and cooperative group work situations and the double role of the teacher, as a teacher and as a researcher of his or her professional action. Finally, the teaching flexibility can be considered a competence, which will allow the educator to adapt the rest of their professional skills and thus achieve a successful and meaningful learning for the students, besides providing them with tools, skills, competences and useful skills that will allow the student extrapolate them to their near reality.

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